

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF CONTROL OVER THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN DIGITIZATION ENVIRONMENT

Jabborova Zulxumor Shuxratovna

Master’s degree student of Nordic International University

Tel number: +998 93 394 17 22

Email: zulxumor200588@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10158426>

Abstract. This article highlights the public's attitude toward the implementation of national projects aimed at improving educational quality. It also discusses changes pertaining to higher education institutions' financial independence, the rise in requirements for students' intellectual and moral preparation, and the creation of a fiercely competitive training environment. All of these factors combine to make education quality the main concern facing these institutions. Additionally, The article briefly analyzes the structure, experience and modern educational programs of the advanced foreign education system, such as Japan, Germany.

Key words: distance education, projects, digital education, knowledge digitization, ICT literacy, education institutions, computer, diversification, country, education, experience. foreign experience, educational inspection, structure, International Assessment.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается отношение общественности к реализации национальных проектов, направленных на повышение качества образования. В нем также обсуждаются изменения, касающиеся финансовой независимости высших учебных заведений, повышения требований к интеллектуальной и моральной подготовке студентов и создания высококонкурентной учебной среды. Все эти факторы в совокупности делают качество образования главной заботой, стоящей перед этими учебными заведениями. Кроме того, в статье кратко анализируется структура, опыт и современные образовательные программы передовых зарубежных систем образования, таких как Япония, Германия.

Ключевые слова: дистанционное образование, проекты, цифровое образование, оцифровка знаний, ИКТ-грамотность, образовательные учреждения, компьютер, диверсификация, страна, образование, опыт. зарубежный опыт, образовательная инспекция, структура, международная оценка.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада аҳолининг таълим сифатини оширишга қаратилган миллий лойиҳаларни амалга оширишга муносабати ёритилган. Шунингдек, олий ўқув юртларининг молиявий мустақиллиги, талабаларнинг интеллектуал ва ахлоқий тайёргарлигига қўйиладиган талабларни ошириш ва юқори рақобатбардош ўқув муҳитини яратилиши билан боғлиқ ўзгаришлар муҳокама қилинади. Бу омилларнинг барчаси биргаликда таълим сифатини ушбу таълим муассасалари олдида турган асосий ташвишга солади. Бундан ташқари, мақолада Япония, Германия каби илғор хорижий таълим тизимларининг тузилиши, тажрибаси ва замонавий таълим дастурлари қисқача таҳлил қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: масофавий таълим, лойиҳалар, рақамли таълим, билимларни рақамлаштириши, АКТ саводхонлиги, таълим муассасалари, компьютер, диверсификация, мамлакат, таълим, тажриба. хорижий тажриба, таълим инспекцияси, тузилиши, халқаро баҳолаш.

Currently, the implementation of national projects in the field of improving the quality of Education his attitude is in the entire public eye. Intellectual and moral of students increased requirements for the preparation of higher education institutions, financial changes related to independence, serious in the training of personnel of higher education institutions creates competitive conditions, which means that the problem of the quality of education is the most important issue in the n higher education institutions. Compliance of student knowledge with state standards, compliance of the educational institution successful activities – every teacher activity- this is the main quality of education today is a branch.

The level of knowledge, skills, qualifications of students, the organization of the educational process and reflects the level of implementation as well as the conditions for its implementation. Hence for it is necessary to determine certain criteria for the functioning of these conditions. First, these are "personnel who solve everything", secondly, material and technical of the educational institution base, and thirdly, educational programs and scientific and methodological work.

Today, however, there is an improvement in the educational process, a more effective form, style and the search for teaching aids, the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, which as a result, the need to improve the quality of education is clearly manifested.

Research results

How to develop a constant interest in science, knowledge, skills of students and it is possible to find the necessary methods that will most help in the formation of their qualifications? Of this for the lesson should be built in such a way that it is as much as possible the tasks of Education, Development, upbringing let the unit solve; carefully select and adjust the teaching material, solve the learning problems creating optimal conditions for making.

In our opinion, the lesson involves independent creative work of students under the guidance of a teacher activation is one of the effective ways to improve the learning process. Therefore, creating an environment that activates the cognitive activity of students and increases the quality of Education must be independent, which includes taking into account the possibilities and abilities of each student we need to develop education. Unfortunately, in our education system for a long time there are real mechanisms that allow students to have an individual approach to independent education was not Maybe the students did not have a strong need for this. But, of the COVID-19 its spread hinders the activity of organizations in almost all sectors of the economy was one of the main obstacles. In particular, the pandemic affects the activities of secondary educational institutions and there were serious restrictions on the activities of higher education organizations. In this regard, in the context of active measures to prevent the further spread of the pandemic maintaining and developing constructive relations between the participants of the educational process there was a need to identify effective means.

Therefore, to form his intellectual and educational potential in higher education development and education of a person who can influence should be given priority. Therefore, revealing the creative potential and individual abilities of students in the future presentation classes in higher education practice for the formation of qualities related to the profession, use of independent educational forms such as conference classes, business games necessary. In this category, the organization of scientific and research work of students is the responsibility of each student helps reveal individuality and creative potential.

Modernization of education in Uzbekistan in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic in European, East Asian and Russian educational organizations in order to maintain quality experiences were studied and put into practice. Form of education in higher education institutions electronic digital technologies that ensure mutual cooperation of teaching staff quickly moved to the online format due to widespread use. This is part of the students' learning process high training and wide freedom of movement, independent education and research of students it was connected with the existence of various forms of provision.

Educational concept

Changing the methods and technologies of teaching at all levels, increasing the importance of those who form the experience of responsible choice and responsible activity of students the need to stimulate independent work and instill practical skills in information highlights. Therefore, by implementing the principles of student-oriented education, there is a need for a new model of Education built on the basis of modern information technologies was. Seeing them as one of the components of a holistic education system, we are guided by the information we facilitate access, open opportunities for changing educational activities, and the student we will build an educational system that will be an active and equal participant in educational activities. Consequently, the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process is carried out at the modern OSCE we believe that this is one of the ways to improve the quality of Education.

Discussion

The least among the most acute problems associated with the transition to distance education for those who are provided, it is not possible to use modern technologies. For communication some malfunctions of the electronic platforms used, access to the internet network instability, as well as from modern technical resources of professors and teachers' difficulties in its use have affected the quality of Education. We use ICT develops mathematical skills and abilities, increases the level of their culture, we came to the conclusion that it expands the worldview of students. Using a computer teaching management activates the mental activity of students, improves the efficiency of mastering increases and therefore affects the quality of Education. Computer as a training weapon one of the main objectives is to improve the level of education that determines the quality of programming and it consists in organizing student labor using pedagogical tools.

Interactive and interactive computer capabilities motivational of the educational process has a significant impact on the industry and its structure. Spelling or punctuation marks on the computer there are ample opportunities to create comfortable working conditions for understanding. Tables, a variety of visualization in educational programs in the form of diagrams, references forms are not only static in dynamics using graphics, color, sound, icons, etc. allows you to use not only information, but also various languages (English, German, Russian). High the use of ICT in mathematics. Activate students' attention, work forms diversification allows you to increase the creative potential of the individual. In the presentation the construction of diagrams, tables will save time, arrange the material more aesthetically allows to pose. Various interesting tasks allow you to make the lesson more interesting: crosswords, drawings, pictures, tests. Thus, students of higher education institutions are represented by their peers by they were able to watch and evaluate the prepared presentations and provide students with demonstrate not only knowledge of computer technology, but also creative abilities gave the opportunity to do.

In addition, from Information Technology at different stages of training it is advisable to use: in the presentation of new material (Power Point Program); training in stages (different training programs); at the time of control and verification (tested with assessment transfer); during the independent work of students (various educational programs). Thus, the content of the teacher's activity changes: he stops only from the supplier of knowledge, and becomes a developer of new educational technologies. The nature of the student's educational activities also changes dramatically, because it is not only with the teacher and his bandmates, but also with the computer will also be able to communicate. This is one of the main tasks of modern higher education institutions allows you to solve the problem of quality of Education.

Education of our motherland includes comprehensive reforms and reconstruction works he has gone through and is going through a complex process like implementation. Of these the intended goal is to democratize school activities in its, humanitarian the development of principles, the content of educational work on the same basis, its form and consists in a complex update and further improvement of the style. Updated education literally means a new thought, common sense. In the present equal to the dignity, prestige and prestige of education in performers it is also necessary to have Initiative, dedication and business.

The attitude in education will be on the side of most bold movers. Bold movement. And attempt to man, Uzbek national as the classical exponent of pedagogy Abdullah Avlani insisted, the school science can provide enlightenment. From time immemorial, knowledge was valued in us. Those who are knowledgeable are in respect those. Therefore, the service of our country to receive knowledge and receive knowledge serving in the cause is our duty of Supreme humanity. These tasks are relevant one of the important conditions for solving foreign school and pedagogical experiments is learning.

Education through careful and diligent study of international experiences getting rid of hardened, growing forms of work, styles, losing their relevance in addition to being, it has additional rich resources in updating it in a worthy way we will. The head of State said that there is a human resource problem in the country. it was said that the sectors needed modern specialists in line with the pace of reform. To this end, the entire educational system is being improved. Preschool the development is a thorough ground for school lessons. Common middle the quality of education is being improved on the basis of Advanced International experience and modern requirements. Presidential schools, named after our great allies, like specialized schools, creativity schools, Timurbek's schools modern and innovative educational institutions were established. International experiences in them the fact that it has been established indicates that mature cadres will mature in the future. On November 26, 2019, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, announced that the school adopted a resolution “on measures for the establishment of schools”.

In the Address sent by the President to the Oliy Majlis in January of this year improvement of school curricula based on advanced foreign experience, training revision of downloads and subjects, bringing them to international standards he emphasized the need to adapt, improve the quality of textbooks and literature. Improvement of material and technical support in schools, international in the educational process defined the tasks of applying modern pedagogical technologies. Only 10 percent of mathematics, chemistry, physics, and biology classes in our country allocated to practical training. In developed countries, this indicator is 30-50 is a percentage. Therefore, the Ministry of Public Education Information Technologies and

Communications wide range of digital technologies in educational programs of the Ministry of Development use, the task of increasing the scope of practical training in specific sciences was set.

Today, the level of development of any nation state and society, first of all, his attention to human capital and human development is a step in this direction measured by actions. Today, attention is paid to the content of education is reaching the conditions in developed countries... This is proof We will analyze the education system of foreign countries:

Japanese education system

There is no concept of `gifted student` in Japanese education. because each student has a special talent. Within the advanced countries, the specific direction of Japanese education occupies a leading position. In particular, the composition of the Japanese educational system is as follows:

Pre-School, Primary School, junior high school, Upper Secondary School, higher education institutions that are part of higher education systems.

In elementary school, teachers teach children to criticize, that is, to criticize the bad aspects of their behavior, the shortcomings of the school. It can be seen from this that the teacher is not limited to teaching only, but also affects the comprehensive development of the child. Japan is the only state within developed countries where teacher salaries are also high among heads of state.

Compulsory education environment. This stage of education includes children from 6 to 15 years old. Financial assistance is provided to children from needy families.

Upper secondary school includes grades 10-11-12, with day, correspondence, evening sections of such schools. In Upper Secondary Schools, students in the entire educational process take 80 Tests. Students are involved in English, technical education and special testing at their own discretion, in addition to compulsory core subjects.

Students from upper and high school or 12 years of ordinary school are admitted to their universities. Admission to universities is divided into 2 stages: the 1st stage is held in a residential area, for which tests are carried out in Japanese, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, sociology, history. Higher education is compulsory in Japan, and it is continuous with professional education related. The role and responsibility of mothers in raising children in Japan is especially great. They consider themselves Noble before the family dynasty and the state so that their children can grow up intelligent, wise and hardworking. In Japan, a lot of methodological manuals and recommendations are published on family education, and a lot of pedagogical advice is given on radio and television.

Home parties in Japanese families are noteworthy. It is a perfect, side-protected device, with a bookcase on the partition, a highlighter, a clock, a pen, paper, a micro calculator and other necessary items, as well as built-in to the alarm buttons that call their parents if necessary. The level of Japanese high schools is slightly higher than the level of US high schools.

As can be seen from the above, the educational system in Japan has acquired high harmony, both in form and content. There are many aspects that are worth learning. Another side of attention is the presence in Japan of such progressive countries as the United States, France, Germany in the world, which are not limited to only national traditions advanced pedagogical work experiences are also creatively assimilated. Such experiments put the educational system of our Republic at a higher level there is no doubt that it will come in handy when lifting.

German education system:

Germany is one of the foci of World enlightenment and culture. In this state, each citizen has the right to freely develop his personality, choose a school, place of study and profession,

depending on the inclination and ability of his talents. The school education system consists of primary and secondary education institutions. All public schools are free to attend. In Germany, School Education is divided into the following school types: primary’s school; orientation schools; basic school; real school; gymnasium; comprehensive school; special school.

Primary school is the foundation of the education system. After elementary school, students switch to directional school. A basic or full Folk School is mandatory for all students who graduate from primary school and do not attend a real school or gymnasium. The teachers of the main school feel that they are social educators, not teachers. But students in the main school are forced to receive a professional education, despite poor mastering share. Real schools are affiliated to the second phase and usually include grades 5-10. The Real school provides a higher level of extended general education and prepares students for vocational training courses so that they have a profession that places a high demand on independent thinking, a sense of responsibility, human leadership skills.

German education has a very complex system with a specific direction. Justifying himself in obtaining a seat in the German state from among the progressive states there is an incoming education system.

Conclusion.

Solving the problem of the quality of education to the changes of the external environment of educational institutions, how timely and objectively respond to the needs of society, social procedures, how effective and pedagogically based methods and technologies depend on the choice that.

REFERENCES

1. Галиуллин Р.Ф. Развитие предпринимательства в вузах России // Вестн. Удмурт. унта. 2015. Т. 25. Вып. 3. С. 15–21.
2. Кайль Я.Я., Епинина В.С., Ламзин Р.М. Основные тенденции и проблемы развития GR-менеджмента // Государственное и муниципальное управление. Ученые записки СКАГС. 2017. № 3.
3. Ikromov A.B., Maxmudov S.Y., Anorqulova G.M. Germaniya: Ta’lim, ilmfan (metodik qo’llanma. Kasb mahorati jurnali -2004-yil. 2 son.
4. Yo’ldoshev J.F. Xorijda ta’lim (metodik qo’llanma) - Toshkent: 1995- yil
5. A.Nosirov. Fransiyada talim sifati qanday nazorat qilinadi? -, , Boshlang’ich ta’lim“ jurnali. 2019- yil. 12- son.
6. Ламзин Р.М., Наумова Е.Ю. Функциональные ресурсы современного публичного управления // Инновационные методы решения социально-экономических проблем образования и науки: сб. ст. по итогам Всерос. конкурса исследоват работ магистрантов и аспирантов. Уфа, 2017. С. 13–16.
7. R.Ilashova. Amerika maktablarida.- , , Boshlang’ich ta’lim” jurnali. 2019- yil. 3-son.;
8. G.Anorqulkova, A. Karimov.Xorijiy mamlakatlar ta’lim tizimining o’ziga xos yo’nalishi uslub va tahlili. Xalq ta’limi ilmiy metodik jurnali. 2017-yil. 3-son